
USE AND APPLICATION OF ICT IN LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

ICT has key Impact and effect in the environment of library and Information Centers. The libraries are now well equipped with ICT Infrastructure and Staff also using ICT for caring out different library activities .Due to ICT it is possible for libraries to provide right information to right user at right time form the globally distributed resources. Information communication Technology (ICT) and Web Technologies have changed the traditional concept of libraries. Today the Digital world is Concerned with creation, sharing and using information in digital form. 21st century the book are not our means of preservation but also for dissemination of the information contained in them Now days most of function carried out by the libraries have been modernized with new technology .This paper highlights use and Application of ICT and Web Technologies in libraries.

Keyword: *ICT, Use ICT in Library, Application Of ICT, Web technologies, Application of Web technology In libraries*

Introduction:

This paper focused on use and Application of ICT and web technologies in libraries. This concepts is new as well as important to all people as library users. Information Technology (IT) is the modern buzz word; it has provided facilities for the free flow of Information. The world has become a global village with Information super highways created through networks Internet. New technology development has already profoundly affected libraries. All most every function carried out in a library has been altered to some extend by advances in electronics, computerization and telecommunication in ICT and web technology.

Definition of ICT:

The term information technology is manipulated in many ways. The utilization of computer based technology and internet in order to retrieve and disseminate the information rapidly is nothing but the ICT. The term ICT includes any communication devices or application, on compassing radio, TV, Cellular Phones, Computer and network, hardware and Software, Satellite Systems and so on. The Technology evolution in libraries in libraries has been called a “Quit revolution”(Abdas Scatter 1997).

The Information processing, storing and dissemination with the Information technology (IT)(Brown 1983)

“Information Technology as acquisition, Processing, Storage and dissemination of vocal, verbal, pictorial,

textual and numerical information by microelectronic based combination of computer and telecommunication”(Macmillan Dictionary).

Use Information Communication Technology in Libraries:

In recent years access to computer and the Internet has become an unavoidable necessity for every institution of higher learning and research. The internet was used in libraries for searching for information e-mail accessing databases, down loading software providing a current awareness service and accessing e-journals and e-books, Reference service, Bibliographic service, Current Awareness Service, Document Delivery Inter Library loans and Union catalogues.

Services Providing To The Library Users:

Today in library User demand first services in digital world and librarian providing following services to the user

Information Services:

In the computer era, we are surrounded by automated digital and virtual libraries as most of the libraries are now making use of ICT based resource services FTP, Telnet, WWW, Search engines, System Software, electronic News letters, webpage, CD's, DVD, have become an integral part of the library.

Bibliographic Services:

In this database is available in electronic form on CD Rom or Online efficient and cost effective information retrieval efficient and cost effective information. Retrieval dialog, the popular database companies on CDROM and online platform Implement and Publication the project to evaluate their effectiveness.

Audiovisual Services:

Audio Visual Materials are playing an important role to access the information audio visual material are available in the form of music, Pictures, films etc. The new multimedia of audio, CD, Video and Digital video Disk have higher storage capacity.

E-Journal:

Electronic journal helps the librarians in addressing these problems to a great extent without significantly affecting the service levels most of libraries are providing e-books and e-Journals. Infolibnet provides e-books and e-journals to college libraries.

Application of ICT:

1. Optical Technology:

Compact discs are one of the most important and useful electronic media of storage information. A CD-Rom can store a huge amount of records of library like Ramayan and Mahabharat.

2. Barcode Technology:

Barcode technology can be defined as a self-contained message with information encoded in series of black bars of varying widths and white space between every two of them it is very helpful of circulation book and stock verification work in the library.

3. Communication Technology:

Communication technology tools very useful in library like telephone, fax, television, e-mail and Internet.

4. Multimedia Technology:

Multimedia a technology is most commonly application to use of sound, text, image and video in preparing presentations and use in.

Web Technology:

Today Web technology in library use full to library user communication. Dr.

S. R. Ranganathans five law the function for the web by defining a minimum requirement. web technologies and its relevance of Ranganathans law

1. Web Resources are for use
2. Every users his or her web resource
3. Every web resources its user
4. Save the time of the user
5. The web is a growing organism.

Application of Web Technology in Library:

Instant Messaging:

Instant Messaging is a form of real time communication between two or more people typed text or image. Question form user and vice user, Online meeting to HOD in any department. Library to Users providing virtual reference service.

Blogs:

A Blog is a website where someone regulation record their thoughts or experience talk about a subject Blog making in library Brief Summary or a library website linking. A typical blog combining text, image and link to other blogs. Blogs can also use for the collection development where the users request the resources. Blogs can serve as discussion form.

RSS (Really simple syndication):

Announcement of the availability of new book and other resources in a given subject area.. Library users Information sending events ,Organized Programmes. Library Readers Announce availability of new resource learning.

Wikis:

Wikis web technology offer to sharing knowledge and information. Internet communication medium for sharing information and amanges the library staff and students. Reference resource wiki can be built.

Tagging:

The concept of tagging has been widened for beyond website bookmark and servies line flickr(Photo),Youtube (video),Audio. It is a digital object.

Social Networking:

Today increasing use social Networking User contact can be added to the library catalogue including users book revives other communication. Libraries can create a page to reach to new users.

Social Book Mark:

Library among users sharing web resources. e.g. Bibliographic distribution lists. Sharing resources which other users.

Podcasting:

Podcasting application in library oral presentation. Podcast highlights about new resource. It is a series of video digital media files.

Conclusion:

The role of librarians is continuing to evolve with the adoption of internet and World Wide Web in to the profession of librarianship. Library and Information centers play avital role providing the information required to the users for their research and development activities. Libraries are transforming quickly due to ICT and web technology.

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